

APPLICATION OF MODERN MARKETING ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE RELEASE OF NEW PRODUCTS AT ENTERPRISES

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***Annotation:** The use of marketing tools at the stage of introducing a new product to the market is considered. It is shown that for the successful and effective implementation of a new product, it is necessary to use innovative marketing technologies in innovation management.*

***Keywords:** marketing, new product, market, innovative marketing.*

Introduction

In the harsh modern conditions of hypercompetition, the market is forced to continuously find new marketing technologies, in contrast to traditional forms of marketing. There are many new directions in marketing activities and, accordingly, many new concepts - benchmarking, outsourcing, merchandising, Internet marketing, brand marketing, relationship marketing, etc. A feature of innovative marketing technologies is that they do not work with a physically existing product, but with its concept being developed. The concept of the innovation life cycle appears, which includes several stages of its creation. Scientific and technical work of a fundamental and applied nature, experimental design work are being carried out, and the cycle ends with the stage of mastering production. Then classic, or traditional, marketing comes into play. In contrast to the production process, the innovation process is characterized by: numerous and uncertain ways to achieve the goal and high risk; the impossibility of detailed

planning and focus on predictive estimates; the need to overcome resistance, both in the sphere of existing economic relations and the interests of the participants in the innovation process.

Innovative marketing remains an underestimated area of innovation activity in Uzbekistan. At Uzbek enterprises, it is considered at best as a management function with limited use of a set of marketing tools, and its important aspect is overlooked – it allows assessing the management system of an innovative enterprise and its strategy from the point of view of long-term development. At present, enterprises engaged in innovative activities are faced with the need to analyze competition in the market, analyze innovation from the consumer's point of view, functional cost analysis, conduct market research of the innovation market, position innovations in markets and reposition, analyze pricing and price structure , analysis of potential industrial consumption and demand for innovations, formation of a sales delivery system, organization of service and warranty services, development of sales promotion methods and advertising and analysis of its effectiveness. All these functions are intended to be performed by innovative marketing - a new and not adapted phenomenon in modern Uzbek reality. Innovative marketing should help to intensify the innovative activity of Uzbek enterprises at the present stage.

After the concept of the product has been developed and the company's management has decided to release it, the marketing service must organize work to bring the product to the market. At the stage of implementing an innovation into full-scale production and sale, it is necessary to answer a number of the following questions.

Time to bring the product to market. If a new product results in a reduction in sales of existing products, then its release may be delayed. However, it must be remembered that competitors may release a similar product, and you may be in danger of losing the market. Technically sophisticated products that hit

the market on time are more profitable than those that come out much later than planned. A McKinsey study concludes that a six-month delay in product release results in a 33% reduction in product lifecycle profit, and a 30% project development team budget overrun means only a 30% loss in profit. 2%.Materials and methods.

Place of implementation. A new product may be offered for sale in a local, regional or international market. The size of the market depends on the scale of the company's activities. Larger companies can develop several regions at once. If an innovative project is developed with limited possibilities, then the commercial implementation of the product should be carried out in a separate region.

Target market selection. When releasing a product for commercial sale, it is necessary to determine the target group of consumers, because each of them perceives innovations differently. First of all, when introducing a product to the market, the company will focus on “innovator” buyers, and it is on them that the perception of the novelty product by other categories of the population depends. In the industrial market, perception is based on the opinion of the industrial consumer, and the decision to purchase a product is made after there is a need for it for the release of the company's products.

Promotion action plan. You need to develop an action plan to bring the product to market. The appearance of a product on the market should be accompanied by advertising and information support. In addition, it is necessary to determine the places and conditions of sale. The following questions should be answered: how will the consumer receive the product (at the point of sale, by mail, ordering a catalog, via the Internet, etc.); who will serve consumers, what information and what knowledge sellers should have; how intense the market coverage will be, how many intermediaries can be included in the distribution channel.

Forecasting new product sales. The marketing service must give a forecast

of sales when penetrating the target market and evaluate their volume corresponding to the achievement of a given profitability, taking into account the costs of marketing support. At the first stage of the marketing analysis, sales volumes are estimated during the first three years after the release. For this purpose, expert research methods and methods based on sales in the control market can be applied.

Expert assessments formulated by marketing specialists are based on information collected at the preliminary analysis stage and take into account data on competitor sales, potential market size, global demand, market shares of various brands, distribution network availability, etc. Opportunity studies aim to actively collect the missing information through direct interviews with potential users, merchants, suppliers and, if possible, competitors. A market test, or test sale, during which the actual market behavior of buyers is observed, allows you to assess the level of trial and repeat purchases and the volume of potential sales of a new product. You can also conduct trial sales at the place of residence or experiments in special laboratories-shops.

These methods are usually used together. Using any of the above or some other approach, the marketing function must establish a target sales volume. This requires the development of a launch strategy based on the analysis of many options for a basic plan.

Market penetration profiles. The evolution of the demand for a new product over time will be different for products such as equipment that is bought only once, products with a long service life, or consumer goods.

For a one-time purchase, the expected sales volume first rises steadily, reaches a maximum, then falls steadily until there are no potential buyers left.

The key variable here is the level of market coverage. Demand for a durable good breaks down into demand for first purchase and demand for repurchase. The determinants of both components of demand are different. The demand for the first

purchase is determined by the phenomena of copying and diffusion, which often depend on time. The demand for a replacement depends on the aging of the product. Demand for everyday goods can also be decomposed into two components: the first and repeat purchases.

The number of people who buy a product for the first time first rises and then declines, as most buyers have already experienced the product. An important criterion is the level of repeat purchases, since it determines the buyers who are loyal to the product. Eventually sales will reach a constant level. For products of this type, the frequency of purchase is the best measure of satisfaction.

Estimation of expected market share. Information on market shares by regions, segments, distribution channels can be obtained from surveys of buyers and dealers. Based on these data, the increase and decrease in market shares can be interpreted.

The market share decomposition model proposed by Parfitt and Collins allows you to quickly build a market forecast for a new product with a high frequency of purchases based on the database provided by an organized consumer group. Market share can be broken down into three components:

product penetration rate - the total percentage of buyers who made a trial purchase in period t . At first it grows, and then, as the “stock” of buyers is depleted, it stabilizes; repeat purchase rate - the percentage of total sales that are accounted for by customers who have already made a trial purchase. After several periods of purchase, this level reaches an equilibrium; Intensity level - a comparison of the average quantities purchased by a customer of a product with the average quantities purchased by a single customer in a given product category. The product of these three components gives an estimate of the expected market share. Let's assume that the estimates for penetration and repeat purchases are 3.4% and 2.5%, respectively; at the same time, the average volume of purchases of a new brand is the same as for the entire product category. Then the expected

market share will be:

$$3,4 \% \cdot 2,5 \% \cdot 1,00 = 8,5 \%$$

This definition of market share allows us to understand the possible reasons for the dynamics observed in the structure of the market. Thus, the reduction in market share can be explained by the fact that: the product is losing consumers (the level of market penetration decreases); for the purchase of this product, a smaller share of purchases in the product category is made (the level of repeated purchases decreases); buyers purchase this product in smaller quantities than the average for the product category (lower intensity of purchases).

When analyzing the success of the development of a product after its introduction to the market, three critical points are usually considered, which the analyst must distribute over time, based on the adopted strategy. These points are shown in fig. 1. Simple break-even point (TPB): the moment when the process of releasing a new product leaves the loss zone and begins to make a profit. Global Break-Even Point (GBB): the moment when the adjusted total revenue exceeds the adjusted total costs; the firm returned its investment. Product Capital Accumulation Point (CPP): the point at which a new product has brought in funds sufficient to invest in a project to extend the product's life cycle or in other projects of the firm.

Ideally, the point of capital accumulation should be before the maximum point on the product life cycle curve so that the firm has time to prepare to release an improved or new product at the right time in response to market pressure and competition. These three criteria, defined in a dynamic perspective, are useful for assessing the acceptability of any new project from an economic point of view.

It is often helpful to be clear about risk assessments and project quality criteria. To do this, you can build a matrix for evaluating new product projects. Projects in this matrix are ranked along two axes: position along the horizontal axis determines the attractiveness of the project for the firm; the position on the

vertical axis is given by the probability of the technological and commercial success of the project as assessed by the firm's management at the end of the research and analysis phase.

As a result, projects are positioned in four quadrants:

- in the upper right quadrant are "pearls" - projects with a high probability of success and very attractive to the company;

- in the lower right quadrant are "blooming buds", or potential "pearls" - projects that are attractive to the company, but still with a low probability of success;

- in the upper left quadrant there are projects with a good probability of success, i.e. with little risk, but of little interest to the firm: "porridge bowls." The projects are unattractive, but still worthy of consideration.

- finally, in the lower left quadrant are "lost cases":

projects with low probability of success and of little interest to the firm.

Analysis of the project portfolio allows you to select projects and identify priority actions, for example: to focus resources on the development and launch of "pearl" projects; increase the competitiveness of bud projects by deepening preliminary studies and analyzes to better define the concept; reduce the number of "porridge bowls", which often take up too much time and resources; exclude from the portfolio projects - "lost cases".

The path of innovation is fraught with risk. There may be several reasons.

1. Insufficient distinctive characteristics of the goods. This indicator is often decisive in providing a new product with an advantage over competitors.

2. Insufficiently clear definition of the market or product prior to its actual development. Ideally, a new product should be developed on the basis of a well-defined protocol-statement, which establishes:

- a) a clearly defined target market;

b) specific preferences of consumers in this market; c) properties and purpose of the goods.

3. Reassessment of the degree of an attractive market. When searching for target niches, the selected market segment is too small and saturated with competitors to justify the cost of creating a new product.

4. The high cost of the product development process.

5. Significant time investment. From the moment ideas are generated to the moment a prototype is created, a long period of time can pass. During this period, similar products may appear on the market, and the company's product will no longer be perceived as new.

6. Unforeseen costs in the product development process.

7. Inefficient implementation of the marketing mix.

Thus, the activity of any enterprise will not be as effective if the enterprise does not introduce innovative marketing technologies. Innovative marketing uses a set of tools and methods that enable an enterprise to timely and correctly assess its chances to introduce an innovative product with maximum efficiency. Innovative marketing technologies, predicting the relevant market segments, planning the consumer properties of innovation, price, distribution channels, advertising costs, can reduce market uncertainty and the risk of consumer rejection of innovation.

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